

Demographics

How would you describe your position (check all that apply)?

- I develop software for science or engineering applications
- I use science and engineering software developed by others
- I conduct research
- I engage in engineering activities
- I manage or supervise the work of people who do any of the above

Do you regularly use expertise in programming to advance research? This includes researchers who spend a significant amount of time programming, full-time software engineers writing code to solve research problems, and those somewhere in-between.

- Yes
- No

How many years of professional experience do you have?

- Less than a year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- 20+ years

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- High school diploma or equivalent
- Associate's degree (e.g., community college degree)
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate degree (Ph.D., MD, JD, etc.)
- Other:

How much experience do you have with software development?

- I have no experience or knowledge in software development.
- I have a limited understanding and would need assistance with software development tasks.
- I have a moderate level of experience and can complete basic tasks independently.
- I have a significant amount of experience and can handle complex tasks.
- I am highly experienced and could mentor others in software development.

Can you think of a current or previous software project to which you have either contributed either technical content or had a managerial role?

If you have contributed to more than one project, choose the one with which you are most familiar.

- Yes, I can think of a project.
- No, I cannot think of a project.

Describe the research domain of the project.

- Text Entry

How would you describe your role in this project?

- I write and develop new code
- I performed project management tasks
- I was in charge of maintaining compliance
- I am an end-user for this project
- I tested the software
- I find and fix bugs in the software
- I perform maintenance on the software by modifying existing code
- I perform DevOps tasks
- I perform user support tasks (i.e. Help-desk support)
- I perform software security tasks

Which of the following best describes the status of your project?

- Early research stages
- Very exploratory (e.g., proof of principle)
- Somewhat exploratory (e.g., working prototype)
- Somewhat productionized (e.g., somewhat stable but actively evolving)
- Very productionized (e.g., regularly released, maintained)
- Other:

Approximately how many team members are/were on the project?

- 1 Person
- 2-3 People
- 4-5 People
- 6-10 People
- 11-15 People
- 16-20 People
- 21-25 People
- 26+ People

Approximately how many full-time employees (FTEs) are/were allocated to the project?

- Less than 0.5
- 0.5 to 1.49
- 1.5 to 2.49
- 2.5 to 3.49
- 3.5 to 4.49
- 4.5+
- I Don't Know

What percentage of your team has/had a formal (e.g. classroom, training course, or mentorship) background or training in software development?

- None
- A quarter or less
- About half
- Three-quarters or more
- All
- I Don't Know

Security Culture

The remainder of the questions focus on understanding how you view cyber security within your projects. This section is answered on the likert-scale.

Attitude

- I believe software security is an important factor in achieving project success.
- Software security is important to my work in software development.
- The requirements for software security do not interfere with my ability to get the job done.

Behavior

- I make the software components behave in a secure manner despite unexpected inputs or user actions.
- I adhere to security principles and secure coding practices.
- When I do my work, I assume that the software might be misused to reveal bugs that could be exploited maliciously.

Competency

- I know the principles and best practices for secure software development.
- I can quickly identify specific coding errors or security vulnerabilities while examining the code base.
- I can apply methods or techniques adaptive to my project to prevent exploits against vulnerabilities.

Subjective Norms

- I believe the community can govern the security of the software products.
- Members of the community help each other solve security issues.
- I am encouraged to work securely by members of the community.

Governance

- There is a security team (or at least one member) who deals with software security for the project.
- The project has a general policy for software security management (vulnerability reporting, security testing, etc.).
- The project has implemented secure coding practices (coding style, library, API, etc.).

Communication

- There are dedicated communication channels (mailing list, forum, etc.) related to security subjects in the community.
- It is easy for me to find specific security information in the community.
- I know where to go for advice related to a software security issue in the community.

Vignettes

In the following section, you will be shown three vignettes. Vignettes are stories that depict a scenario. Please imagine yourself as the software developer in these scenarios, even if the exact context would be impossible or unrealistic for your job/research.

These vignettes are shown incrementally. You will answer questions as the story continues. As the vignette continues, new text will be displayed in a different color.

Vignette 1

In the next year, there is a large festival that is being planned in one of two locations, Location A and Location B, and is expected to have a significant impact on the local economy of where it is held. Due to the logistics involved, you have been contracted to model the weather patterns for both locations in order to determine the location that is least likely to suffer from bad weather. You develop a plan to utilize open-source software to gather and analyze historic weather data that is kept on a shared drive to create an accurate weather model. The next time you report on your development progress to your sponsor, you include the use of this open-source weather framework and your plan for storing and accessing the weather data necessary for analysis.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- When utilizing external data sets, I verify the authenticity of the data periodically throughout the project.
- I am likely to update my data sets while working on a project.
- When updating to the latest version of a dataset, I verify that the updated data is statistically similar to previous data sets.

Vignette 1 Continued

In the next year, there is a large festival that is being planned in one of two locations, Location A and Location B, and is expected to have a significant impact on the local economy of where it is held. Due to the logistics involved, you have been contracted to model the weather patterns for both locations in order to determine the location that is least likely to suffer from bad weather. You develop a plan to utilize open-source software to gather and analyze historic weather data that is kept on a shared drive to create an accurate weather model. The next time you report on your development progress to your sponsor, you include the use of this open-source weather framework and your plan for storing and accessing the weather data necessary for analysis.

Assume that development goes as planned, you run the simulations and publish your findings. Because of your results, Location A is selected as the better location.

Upon analyzing your findings, the mayor of Location B claims that your published data does not match your findings and claims you were unfairly adjusted the results in favor of Location A. When you begin to verify your findings, you realize that the data no longer matches your claims, forcing you to publish an amendment to your findings, finding Location B the more favorable location. The festival is held at Location B, and Location B is noted as having a significant surge in economic activity as a result.

Unbeknownst to you after hearing about your development plan, the mayor of Location B hired a 3rd-party hacker to maliciously modify the data that you planned to use for analysis to change the results of the study to favor Location B over Location A.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- It is my responsibility to consider malicious actions like this during development.
- This is a scenario I have considered during my work.
- Do you think that this scenario could occur in your domain?

Vignette 2

You are working on a software application that involves analyzing sensitive personal health data. Due to its use of sensitive health data, you are subject to all typical HIPAA constraints.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- Before and during development, I model the flow of data throughout my program to ensure compliance to special requirements.

Vignette 2 Continued

You are working on a software application that involves analyzing sensitive personal health data. Due to its use of sensitive health data, you are subject to all typical HIPAA constraints.

In order to complete the application, you make use of open-source tools and frameworks that your colleagues have recommended from other, unregulated projects.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- When using open-source components, I review the component AND its dependencies to ensure they meet all requirements for my application.
- I test open-source components to ensure that they are not exporting unnecessary information.
- During development, I organize my components to only perform certain tasks

Vignette 2 Continued

You are working on a software application that involves analyzing sensitive personal health data. Due to its use of sensitive health data, you are subject to all typical HIPAA constraints.

In order to complete the application, you make use of open-source tools and frameworks that your colleagues have recommended from other, unregulated projects.

Your colleagues have had positive experiences with these components, and did not notice any suspicious activity. You successfully complete your application and finish the project. Unbeknownst to you, one of the open-source components you are using has a dependency that reaches out to external services to assist with calculations. Data leakage is normally not a problem, and has not been a problem for your other colleagues who do not work under special constraints. But because you are working on data that requires HIPAA compliance, when an audit occurs, you are found to be leaking sensitive data that breaks your compliance.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- It is my responsibility to consider malicious actions like this during development.
- This is a scenario I have considered during my work.
- Do you think that this scenario could occur in your domain?

Vignette 3

You are speaking at a conference about some upcoming work that is both novel and exciting. Your work involves using a new algorithm that you developed which decreases the time required to perform calculations over a large data set. You release your work as an open-source tool that other researchers are able to use.

As other researchers begin to adopt your tool, you are contacted urgently from several small research labs and independent researchers that report that they have experienced a severe impact on the performance of their machines, resulting in an accelerated rate of hard-drive failures. When you analyze the tool's code, you realize that you recently posted an update that increases unnecessary read/writes to the system hard-drive under certain conditions, thus decreasing performance and damaging hard-drives.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- Before and during development, I model how my software interacts with other components.
- I consider how my software is supposed to function before development.
- I incorporate controls to ensure that my software functions properly under different sets of conditions, even if they are not conditions I experience.

Vignette 3 Continued

You are speaking at a conference about some upcoming work that is both novel and exciting. Your work involves using a new algorithm that you developed which decreases the time required to perform calculations over a large data set. You release your work as an open-source tool that other researchers are able to use.

As other researchers begin to adopt your tool, you are contacted urgently from several small research labs and independent researchers that report that they have experienced a severe impact on the performance of their machines, resulting in an accelerated rate of hard-drive failures. When you analyze the tool's code, you realize that you recently posted an update that increases unnecessary read/writes to the system hard-drive under certain conditions, thus decreasing performance and damaging hard-drives.

As a result, the tool loses popularity, and another tool is created by someone in the community that is able to capture better success.

Answer the following questions on the likert-scale:

- It is my responsibility to consider malicious actions like this during development.
- This is a scenario I have considered during my work.
- Do you think that this scenario could occur in your domain?

Summary

In the previous three vignettes, we portrayed three types of threats that research software can face: an attack on accuracy, the leaking of private data, and a negative impact on performance. A cyber security attack is defined by NIST's Computer Security Resource Center (CSRC) as "Any kind of malicious activity that attempts to collect, disrupt, deny, degrade, or destroy information system resources or the information itself." During these vignettes, we presented different scenarios where vulnerabilities are created either maliciously or accidentally. NIST's CSRC defines vulnerability as "a flaw or weakness that may allow harm to occur to an IT system or activity."

In the first scenario, two malicious actors, the mayor of Town B and the hired hacker, intentionally impacted the results of the research software to benefit themselves economically. In the second scenario, the developer of the project unintentionally leaked sensitive health information to a third party, whereas in the third, the developer accidentally attacked other researcher's infrastructure with poorly optimized software.

In these examples, we illustrate that these threats not only can affect you and your work but other people and their work, even if you are acting in good faith.

While these situations are fictionalized, they are very real threats that can have very real impacts in the real world. For instance, Vignette 1 is based on a real event involving climate change research. Up to this point we have intentionally avoided the use of technical cyber security terminology. We now "pull back the curtain" and explain how you, as the developer, can increase the security of and reduce threats to your research software by following a process called "Threat modeling" during development.

A threat model is an artifact that assists software engineers to identify and document potential security threats associated with a software product.

While creating a threat model, you typically perform the following actions early into the development phase of your software:

Creating graphical representations of how components interact

- Compartmentalizing application components
- Visualizing the flow of data throughout the application
- Validating the input/output of application components
- Validating the dependencies of the third-party components

In the first scenario: Validating the authenticity and integrity of data entering or leaving an application would assist in protecting the accuracy of your research software.

In the second scenario: Creating graphical representations of how components interact and how data flows through the system would assist in catching a dependency that is either accidentally or maliciously exfiltrating data from your research software. In addition, validating the dependency itself and compartmentalizing it to the minimum amount of access or data would reduce the risk of data leakage.

In the third scenario, graphical representations of component interactions and how data is stored/accessed in the system would have helped the developer identify the problem before the damage was done. When shared, the graphical models would also assist consumers of the software in identifying unique problems they could face that the original developer never considered.

By performing these actions during the design phase or early development, many problems and threats can be addressed with minimal extra effort from the developer.

I already incorporate some or all of these actions into my development process, even if I did not use those specific terms. If yes, select all (if any) actions that you already incorporate into your development process, even if you would not use those specific terms.

- Creating graphical representations of how components interact
- Compartmentalizing application components
- Visualizing the flow of data throughout the application
- Validating the input/output of application components
- Validating the dependencies of the third-party components

1. Creating graphical representations of how components interact
2. Compartmentalizing application components
3. Visualizing the flow of data throughout the application
4. Validating the input/output of application components
5. Validating the dependencies of the third-party components

Please answer the following questions regarding the Threat modeling actions above.
(answers are on the likert scale)

- These actions would fit well in the context of my development process.
- I would need further training to perform these actions during my development process.
- I would be interested in learning how to perform these actions.
- I see the value of performing these actions during my own development.